

Minutes of the 45th Experimenters' Meeting
The Cosener's House, Abingdon, Wednesday 23rd June 2010
(This document was finalised on 23rd August 2010)

Present:

Dr Helen Clark ²	(HAC)	
Dr Catherine Gaffard ³	(CG)	
Dr David Hooper ^{4,5}	(DAH)	Secretary
Mr Dan Housley ⁶	(DJH)	
Dr Dirk Klugmann ³	(DK)	
Dr John Nash ³	(JN)	
Dr Emily Norton ⁶	(EGN)	
Dr Graham Parton ^{1,5}	(GAP)	
Dr Hugo Ricketts ⁶	(HMAR)	
Prof Geraint Vaughan ⁶	(GV)	Chair
Mr Charles Wrench ^{4,5}	(CLW)	

¹British Atmospheric Data Centre (BADC)

²Defence Science and Technology Laboratory (DSTL)

³Met Office (MO)

⁴NERC MST Radar Facility

⁵Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (RAL)

⁶University of Manchester (UofM)

Other abbreviations used in this document:

BL(WP)	Boundary-Layer (Wind-Profiler)
CEDA	Centre for Environmental Data Archival (of which the BADC is a part)
DNS	Domain Name Server
DPW	Dave Wareing (University of Manchester technician)
DWD	Deutscher Wetterdienst
FAAM	(NERC/MO) Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements
FGAM	(NERC) Facility for Ground-based Atmospheric Measurement (formerly UFAM)
FUND	Future Upper-Air Network Development (a Met Office project)
GPS	Global Positioning System
LD	Les Dean (part-time MSTRF site technician)
MST(R)(F)	Mesosphere-Stratosphere-Troposphere (Radar) (Facility)
NCAS	(NERC) National Centre for Atmospheric Science
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NOAA	(US) National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
RMS	root mean square
S/N	signal-to-noise ratio
UPS	Uninterruptable Power Supply

1. Minutes of the previous meeting

The minutes of the previous meeting were accepted without correction.

2. Matters arising

ACTION ITEM 43.3.1 JN to inform DAH of the days on which the Aberystwyth MST radar failed to measure strong winds and DAH to investigate the cause of this failure.

DISCONTINUED

JN reported that he had re-examined the case studies and had found that the problem was not quite as he had first thought. He did not think that the radar observations were at fault. DAH reported, as an aside, that radar/model wind comparison statistics were generated by Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD) for individual days (Met Office statistics cover entire months). He and Volker Lehmann, from DWD, have recently discussed collaborating on a project to investigate the days for which the statistics show large discrepancies. The relative extents to which limitations in the radar data and limitations in the model wind fields contribute to these discrepancies remain to be established.

ACTION ITEM 43.4.1 GV to provide DAH, by the time of the 44th meeting, with sample computer code used by members of his (GV's) group to read MSTRF data from netCDF files. DAH to make the sample code available through the Facility's website as soon as possible.

COMPLETED

The code can now be found by following the "DATA" menu on the website.

ACTION ITEM 44.3.1 DAH to distribute, as soon as possible, the updated version of the Facility's Risk Assessment to all interested parties and to make the document which describes the Facility's location publicly available through the website.

COMPLETED

The updated Risk Assessment has been distributed by e-mail and the 1 page document describing the Facility's location is now available through the "MISCELLANEOUS" menu on the website.

ACTION ITEM 44.4.1 DAH to correct the date-time information in the cloud base altitude files and the quick-look plots stored on the BADC and to alert users to the fact when this has been done.

COMPLETED

The date-time stamp for data messages produced by the Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer is derived from its internal, free-running clock. This suffered from some sort of glitch, on 8th January 2010, which effectively reset it. DAH was able to correct the recorded times in the software used to generate the files stored on the BADC. On 29th January 2010, he recreated the data files and quick-look plots for the entire month.

ACTION ITEM 44.4.2 DAH and GAP to ensure that different versions of MST radar data products stored on the BADC are clearly distinguishable and that no old versions are deleted when the reprocessing of the entire observation archive is undertaken.

ONGOING

No new versions of MST radar data files have so far been produced and so this action item has not yet come into effect.

3. Facility Report

3a) Miscellaneous

DAH reported that the padlock for the site's main gate had become unreliable and so had needed to be replaced in May 2010. Keys for the new padlock have already been distributed to those who are most-frequently on site.

Honey Bees have recently set up a hive within the structure of the wooden shed. DAH could not see any evidence of them inside the shed and so assumes that the hive is between the inner and outer walls. The bees are using the hole vacated by an old water pipe for access. DAH emphasised that Honey Bees are not inherently dangerous, that they fulfil an important ecological role, and that their numbers are declining in the British Isles. Consequently he was pleased that Ceredigion Council, who he had contacted for advice, recommended leaving established colonies as they are (except where there was a threat to people or where other control methods had failed). A member of Aberystwyth University staff, who has bee-keeping connections, recently visited the site. He also recommended leaving the bees untouched. He suspects that they will move of their own accord later in the year since the location of their hive does not leave much room for expansion. In the meantime, anyone visiting the site should be aware of the bees' presence and should avoid the hive entrance area.

Dave Wareing (DPW) and Les Dean (LD) recently found owl pellets at the site. They recommended encouraging the owls as a way of controlling the population of small, cable-chewing mammals. Although their suggestion was not entirely serious, DAH was open to the idea of installing an owl box at the site. LD will investigate this possibility further through his local contacts.

Environmental Science undergraduates from the University of Manchester visited the site, in 2 groups of approximately 20 each, on 15th and 16th April 2010. DAH and GV gave them short talks on the different instruments and on the type of research being undertaken. This year's visits were made particularly significant as they coincided with the closure of UK airspace in response to the spread of volcanic ash (see Section 6a). GV was able to show the students live lidar images of the ash passing overhead.

Allen White, from the US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), visited the UK on 17th and 18th June 2010. DAH took him to visit the Chilbolton Observatory on the first day and arranged for him to give a seminar on "*Atmospheric Applications for UHF Wind Profilers Other than Wind Profiling*" at Reading University on the second.

DAH had reported at the last Experimenters' meeting that a NERC "*Planet Earth*" podcast focusing on the MSTRF was shortly due for publication. It features interviews with GV and DAH and it is now available at <http://planetearth.nerc.ac.uk/multimedia/story.aspx?id=660>.

3b) Electricity

The Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS) units were originally configured to send DAH warning e-mails whenever there was a disruption of the incoming electricity supply. However, this facility stopped working in October 2007, apparently as a result of the designated Domain Name Server (DNS) no longer being available. DAH updated the DNS settings during the first week of March 2010 and has subsequently been made aware of short-lived disruptions (i.e. lasting for less than a minute) on 7 occasions: on 5th and 20th March 2010, 10th April, 22nd and 23rd May, and 6th and 21st June. Equipment can continue to operate for up to half an hour after the loss of the incoming supply, so none of these disruptions was significant.

The UPS unit for one of the transmitters (TX5) began to complain intermittently about a faulty battery pack during the early part of 2010. A replacement pack was installed on 23rd March 2010. It turns out that only one of the batteries from the original pack had failed. Consequently LD was able to transfer the best of the remaining batteries into the pack for the receiver room UPS. This has slightly improved the

latter's storage capacity and therefore the length of time for which equipment can continue to operate after the loss of the incoming supply.

3c) MST Radar renovation

Three engineers from ATRAD, the company which will undertake the renovation work on the MST radar, visited the site during the first week of March 2010. The radar was powered down between 09 UT on 2nd March and 17 UT on 4th March (and again between 10 and 12 UT on 5th March) in order to allow the engineers to undertake a detailed survey of the hardware. Amongst other things, they established that it is possible to transmit the control signals for the new phasing units through the existing radio frequency cables. This obviates the need to install 100 new control cables, which are known to be particularly prone to vermin damage. The ATRAD team are currently designing the new phasing units and it is hoped that installation will take place during autumn 2010.

DAH, together with Jon Eastment and John Bradford (engineers from Chilbolton), conducted a follow-on survey between 7th and 9th June 2010. On this occasion, the radar was restored to working order each evening. The primary purpose of the survey was to establish the standing wave ratio (i.e. the resonance response) of each of the 400 Yagis. Since this was probably the first time in the radar's 20 year lifetime that the Yagis had been disconnected from their existing phasing units, progress was slow. Moreover, the team were in danger of developing blisters on their hands after having disconnected (and reconnected) just a tenth of the Yagis on the first day. DAH emphasised the utility of the tight-fitting, rubber-padded gardening gloves which the team had purchased on the second day of the survey. These allowed them to get a surprisingly good grip on the cables whilst fully protecting their hands from blistering. Even so, the survey could not have been completed in the allotted time (48 hours) without a considerable amount of help from DPW and LD, for which DAH was very grateful. DPW even fashioned a pair of teaspoons into bespoke cable sheath looseners, which proved to be highly-effective. Only 3 out of the 400 Yagis were found to be obviously non-functioning. Nevertheless, several others were found to have slightly unexpected, but not obviously bad, resonance characteristics.

DAH drew attention to the potential use of diurnal variations in spectral noise power as a way of verifying that the renovated radar's beam pointing directions have not changed. Owing to the Earth's rotation, each beam pointing direction sees the pattern of 46.5 MHz galactic emissions along a circle of constant declination, which rotates once every sidereal day - see e.g. <http://www.ann-geophys.net/19/863/2001/>. For the NE6.0 beam, this includes a transit through Cassiopeia-A, which has previously been used to verify the radar's beam width. DAH emphasised that this transit is seen daily, not just on 17th December as had previously been assumed.

4. NERC Instrument Report

The style of the quick-look data plots, which are available through the BADC, has changed slightly since 20th May 2010. An apparently-unrelated software update on one of the BADC's computers caused DAH's "gnuplot" plotting scripts to stop working. DAH was obliged to modify the scripts so that they could be run under an updated version of "gnuplot" (4.4 rather than 4.0) on a different computer. "Anti-aliasing" functionality in the latest software leads to a difference in the appearance of fine-scale features. GV drew attention to the fact that the quick-look plots are a very useful addition to the dataset. He currently has a summer student working on a project, for which all of the necessary radar information can be derived from an inspection of the plots.

4a) Campbell Scientific surface met sensors

LD had to clean out the tipping bucket rain gauge with bleach on the afternoon of 24th March 2010. It had been raining that day and LD noticed that water was accumulating in the collecting bowl rather than draining through. The instrument had last recorded rain on 12th March 2010, although it is not thought to have rained again until 24th. The instrument successfully recorded rain again on the following day.

4b) Campbell Scientific surface wind sensors (Frongoch)

There have been no problems with this instrument for the past 6 months.

4c) Vaisala WXT510 surface met and wind sensors

There have been at least 6 periods (on 27th January 2010, 25th April, 2nd, 5th, 14th, and 16th May) when this instrument failed to record rain which was detected by the tipping bucket rain gauge. In most of these cases the rain was very light. Consequently it is plausible that the droplets were not falling with sufficient momentum to generate a detectable piezo-electric signal. However, the rarity of the WXT510 failing to detect rain in previous years suggests that an instrumental problem may instead be to blame. Power-cycling the instrument is known to have cleared similar problems in the past. However, DAH was reluctant to do this before it was established whether or not the instrument was at fault. Unfortunately there has been a lack of heavy rain, which would allow the ambiguity to be resolved. JN pointed out that an intercomparison of different rain sensors, including the WXT510, had recently been carried out under the auspices of the World Meteorological Organisation (WMO), see e.g. <http://www.adv-geosci.net/25/37/2010>.

Data messages produced by the WXT510 became corrupted sporadically between 08:53 UT on 10th April 2010 and 13:00 UT on 14th April. DAH power-cycled the instrument at 16:26 UT on 14th April. No corrupted data messages have been seen since.

There is a gap in data capture between 10:37 and 12:51 UT on 8th June 2010 owing to the data acquisition computer being rebooted.

4d) Vaisala LD40 laser ceilometer

A quick-look plot of the latest 24 hours' of backscatter data, which is updated every 30 minutes, is now available through the supplementary website. DAH introduced this facility on 23rd April 2010 in support of the search for evidence of volcanic ash - see Section 6a. It is noteworthy that the LD40 was able to detect ash on only one of the many days when the colocated Elight lidar was able to do so. This was on 16th April 2010 when the ash layer had descended to an altitude of below 2 km. DAH pointed out that backscatter data have been recorded since 2007 and that they can be made available upon request. However, he did not want to release the data through the BADC until he (or someone else) has had a chance to calibrate the backscatter powers. This remains a low priority.

4e) Sky camera

There is a gap in image capture between 10:40 and 12:14 UT on 8th June 2010 owing to the acquisition computer being rebooted.

One of DAH's RAL colleagues has recently supervised a work experience student, who has added more details to the sky-camera event log.

4f) MST Radar

Met Office radar/model wind comparison statistics show that the radar data quality has been good for the past 6 months. JN commented on the fact that there had been a small but persistent (over the past 4 months) offset between the radar/model and radiosonde/model statistics for the eastward wind component at altitudes above 10 km. He warned that this could indicate a degradation in the system.

As is typical, there have been a large number of instances of interference which did not cause any contamination of the wind-profile data: 6 in February 2010, 14 in March, 1 in April, 2 in May and 4 in June. There have been only 5 instances when contamination of the wind-profile data did occur: on 25th, 27th and 31st May 2010 and on 1st and 7th June. Acting on DAH's speculation that the interference is caused by over-heating within the receiver chain, LD attached a small fan to the back of the receiver rack on 16th March 2010. However, since this did not lead to an immediate cessation of the problem, the cause

of the interference remains to be established.

LD fitted new extractor fans to the transmitters during February 2010. The previous fans had failed after periods of operation which ranged between only a few weeks and a few months. LD speculates that this was, at least in part, the result of the fans having had to work against an excessive back pressure; the extracted air used to be vented along pipes which exit the site bungalow along its west-facing wall. Consequently LD has disconnected the pipes so that the extracted air is now vented directly into the transmitter room. Moreover, the fans are now fitted on the outsides of the transmitters so that they can be replaced more easily.

The radar was taken out of operation for approximately 1 hour on the morning of 25th May 2010. This was to allow LD to increase the output power settings of the transmitters from level 2 (out of 5) to level 3. The transmitter which powers the central portion of the antenna array did not operate stably at this higher setting and had to be returned to level 2. All other transmitters continue to operate at level 3.

LD fixed a blown choke on transmitter TX1 on the morning of 11th June 2010. It is not known for how long the transmitter had been out of operation.

5. Guest Instrument Report

5a) FGAM instruments - EGN

The boundary-layer wind-profiler (BLWP) was operated at Weyborne, between September 2009 and April 2010, as part of the Coastal Air Pollution (CAP) campaign. It was prone to crashing frequently, but has been much more reliable since its software was updated. Since April 2010 the BLWP has been in operation at Cardington in support of the Met Office's Future Upper-Air Network Development (FUND) campaign. A dedicated clutter screen was built around the entire instrument (i.e. not just around the vertical beam panel) in May 2010. This has led to an improvement in the data quality, especially under conditions of low wind speeds. The BLWP will continue to support the FUND project at Cardington until Autumn 2011, when it will return to Capel Dewi.

DK reported that the Degreane-supplied clutter screen which surrounds the new Met Office BLWP at Chilbolton appears to be of limited effectiveness. JN speculated that this is a result of the BLWP's vertical beam antenna panel being four times the area of a standard one. The geometry of the clutter screen is not optimised for this. Consequently DK has constructed an additional clutter screen, made from chicken wire, around the vertical beam panel. If this proves to be effective, a more-robust solution will be implemented in the future. See Section 6b for further details about this instrument.

5b) University of Manchester static instruments - GV

The static lidar, together with the mobile Elight lidar, was recently operated in support of the Met Office's emergency campaign to detect the presence of volcanic ash - see Section 6a. GV commented on the fact that although he had been happy to help, the work had been unfunded. Lidar observations are not so straightforward to interpret as radar observations and scientific effort is required to analyse them. Consequently it will be difficult to provide the same level of support for any future emergency of this kind unless appropriate funding is made available.

5c) Met Office GPS receiver

DAH reported on behalf of Jon Jones from the Met Office. The Capel Dewi GPS receiver developed a fault during the last 6 months and had to be returned to the manufacturer for repairs. However, owing to corrosion of the antenna/antenna-cable interface, the receiver did not work immediately upon re-installation. Normal operations were only resumed after Jon fitted a new connector. He was extremely grateful to DPW for the help he provided in tracing and then fixing the problem.

The Met Office have discussed using the BADC as an archive for all GPS delay data. However, this is still in the planning stage and anyone who would like access to the data, for non-commercial work, in the near future should contact Jon directly. GAP added that the BADC could potentially host GPS data from a wider range of European stations, which are already contributing to the E-GVAP project. However, this will require agreement from all of the data-contributing organisations before it can go ahead. DK pointed out that that data relating to a single station are actually derived from a network analysis - hence the need for agreement consent from everyone in the network. DAH drew attention to the fact that, according to Allen White's recent seminar (see Section 3a), NOAA always deploy a GPS receiver together with a wind-profiler.

6. Science and technical presentations

6a) Lidar measurements of the Eyjafjallajökull volcanic cloud - GV

Three different lidar systems were used by the UofM group to detect the presence of volcanic ash during April and May 2010. The Leosphere ALS 300 (EZ) lidar is a 355 nm (i.e. ultra-violet) system. It can cover most of the tropospheric depth and features good sunlight rejection. It is small and highly portable. This enabled it to be easily redeployed - from Cardington to Manchester and then to Lerwick - during the volcanic ash observation period. A key attribute turned out to be its dual polarisation capability. This allows a distinction to be made between backscatter from quasi-spherical aerosols, which are typical of the boundary layer (BL), and that from the more-irregularly-shaped ash particles. The system is well-engineered and allows observations to be made using either analogue detection or photon counting.

The Elight Aerosol and Ozone lidar has the possibility of using 5 different wavelengths. However, attention was restricted to 355 nm (using an enhanced repetition rate) for the volcanic ash observations. Although the lidar is capable of very-high-resolution observations, i.e. 7.5 m in the vertical and 1 minute in time, the extent of its vertical coverage is more or less restricted to the depth of the BL. It allows analogue detection only. It was operated exclusively at the MST radar site for the volcanic ash observation period. However, it is mounted on a trailer and so could be redeployed elsewhere.

The static Raman lidar system is permanently housed in the shipping containers at the MST radar site. It transmits high-powered 355 nm pulses and has an overlap at 2 km altitude. Consequently it is able to profile most of the depth of the free troposphere. It employs a photon counting system. It can detect 355 nm aerosol scattering at any time of day or night. However, of particular interest here were the nitrogen returns at 387 nm and the water vapour returns at 407 nm. These can be used for night time observations to derive profiles of water vapour mixing ratio.

Ash was seen frequently over Capel Dewi and Cardington during the periods 13th - 23rd April 2010 and 11th - 17th May. Full details can be found at <http://data.cas.manchester.ac.uk/lidar/>. The ash tended to occur in single, narrow, uniform layers during the first period but in multiple, thicker, patchy layers during the second period. Work has begun on trying to determine the properties of the ash from the lidar observations. A comparison of the Raman lidar returns at 355 and 387 nm gives the lidar (optical extinction to backscatter) ratio. The unexpectedly (and controversially) large mean values for the April period (182) suggest that the ash particles were much larger and darker than those associated with eruptions of Mount Etna (mean lidar ratio values of 55). DK confirmed that similarly large values were found for observations made by an airborne lidar system.

The ultimate aim of this type of work is to be able to define the ash source function, which is required to initiate the dispersion model. For example, how much mass was ejected and to what heights? Moreover, how did the ash particles behave once they are airborne? For example, how quickly, did they start to sediment? DK clarified that high pressure over the British Isles appeared to be the driving force which caused the ash to enter the BL - not sedimentation. In order to improve the interpretation of remote sensing data, more will need to be known about the properties of the ash particles, e.g. their complex

refractive index. It may be necessary to improve the lidar scattering models for this type of particle, e.g. to encompass Mie scattering.

GAP drew attention to a website hosted at the BADC - <http://cedaapp1.badc.rl.ac.uk/> - which pools details of diverse volcanic ash observations. This was created by the development team of the Centre for Environmental Data Archival (CEDA, of which the BADC is a part) for the benefit of the NCAS community. He encouraged the UofM to add details of their lidar observations to this site. He also drew attention to the fact that researchers at RAL were working on the derivation of ash properties from satellite observations.

ACTION ITEM 45.5.1 HMAR to include details of the UofM lidar observations of volcanic ash on the CEDA website as soon as possible.

NEW

6b) Progress with the Chilbolton wind-profiler - JN

Wind data from the new BLWP initially showed a systematic directional bias of around 6° at all altitudes. This turned out to be the result of applying the correction between magnetic and geographic north in the wrong direction; the orientation of the instrument, measured with a magnetic compass, is a required configuration parameter for the processing software. Comparisons with data from 20 radiosondes show that there is a 1 m/s speed bias for BLWP observations made in the low (altitude cover) mode. This is regarded as being acceptable. Wind features can appear at slightly different altitudes in the low and high modes owing to the 375 m range gate separation of the latter.

Vertical velocities are generally well-matched between the two modes. However, it was necessary to tweak the Degreane processing parameters in order to get useful data for 10 minute averaging. EGN pointed out that she needed to use 5 minute averaging for vertical velocities; otherwise the data were of limited use. JN focused on the vertical velocity data for one particular day. An enhancement of signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) coincided with the capping inversion at the top of the BL. A less-well-defined capping layer could be seen rising through the lower altitudes during the later part of the morning. The altitude of the cloud base, as determined by laser ceilometer observations, initially followed the lower capping layer. Although the cloud base soon jumped to the level of the main capping layer, the convective activity - as revealed by the root mean square (RMS) deviations of 20 consecutive vertical velocity profiles - remained largely confined beneath the lower layer. This analysis has been undertaken with a view to creating a new Met Office data product based on the BLWP vertical velocities.

6c) Boundary layer retrieval from wind profiler measurements and comparisons to model data - EGN

Values of BLWP S/N, vertical velocity, spectral width, and horizontal wind can all show characteristic changes at the top of the BL. The Angevine (1994) method defines the top of the BL as the altitude at which the (box-car-smoothed range-squared-corrected) S/N profile shows a peak value. A Pichugina (2009) method primarily looks for the peak in horizontal wind speed, but also considers the variance. The two methods can show good agreement. So far, few studies have focused on the retrieval of BL height during the morning transition. For one particular day, EGN found good agreement between the BL heights given by the Angevine method and by laser ceilometer observations. There was a reasonable agreement with the output of Alan Lapworth's one-dimensional model, although the model suggested a slightly steeper increase in BL height as a function of time. The Angevine method tended to pick out slightly higher layers than Unified Model fields for a different day. This work has focused on observations made at Cardington. A large dataset is also available for observations made at Weyborne. However, owing to the latter's coastal location, the BL is much more active than is seen inland.

JN pointed out that the relatively large beam width of the FGAM BLWP could limit the usefulness of the spectral width data. GV added that Chris Lee's work has shown that spectral widths can be highly vari-

able over short time scales. Moreover, the shape of the signal components can be highly non-Gaussian. Chris has found that where this is the case, there tends to be a poor match between radar and aircraft measurements of turbulence intensity. The match is much better where the radar signal components are more Gaussian. CG indicated that the campaign period of FUND will produce a good dataset for this type of work.

6d) The new Chilbolton Wind Profiler - CG

When the new Met Office BLWP began operations at Chilbolton, the spectra were contaminated with significant amounts of ground clutter - particularly at a range of 600 m, which is assumed to correspond to the big dish. The Met Office think that the Degreane-supplied clutter screen is too low and too far from the vertical beam antenna panel to block its sidelobes (see Section 5a). The off-vertical beams did not appear to be as badly affected, except at heights below 200 m. DK built an additional clutter screen, made from chicken wire, exclusively around the vertical beam panel (EGN pointed out that rabbit wire, unlike chicken wire, is welded and so it has better electrical properties for this sort of application). It rises to just over half a metre above the panel. The wire is cable-strapped to scaffold poles so that it can flex a little in the wind. Any vibrations will only affect observations made within the first range gate. Although some ground clutter is still evident, it is much less of a problem than previously.

CG reported that she commonly sees vertical bands of strong S/N associated with BL downdrafts, but not with updrafts. Similar observations have been reported in the literature. This phenomenon could be, at least in part, responsible for the commonly-reported downward bias in BLWP vertical velocities. Doppler lidar observations should not be affected by this bias since the nature of the scatterers (aerosols) does not change. There is already a HALO-Photonics Doppler lidar at Chilbolton, albeit over 500 m away from the Met Office compound. Although the nature of the vertical velocity activity should be statistically-similar at the two locations, the horizontal separation is too large to make a direct comparison of vertical velocities appropriate. CG is keen to operate a similar lidar system within the Met Office's instrument compound.

6e) Interpolating vertical velocity from off-axis views - JN

JN and CG have been experimenting with a new technique for estimating vertical velocities from off-vertical beam radial velocities. This does NOT involve averaging the radial velocities from complementary beam pointing directions. Instead it assumes that the horizontal wind does not vary significantly over time scales of a few tens of minutes. This implies that any deviations of the observed off-vertical beam radial velocities from their 25 minute means are caused by vertical velocity activity. Clearly this assumption will not be valid under gusty conditions. For one of the test days, this technique shows a clear increase in inferred vertical velocity activity, and in the RMS deviations, during the course of the morning and early afternoon. There is a reasonable agreement between the distributions of interpolated and directly-observed vertical velocities. Once again this line of enquiry could be better addressed if a Doppler lidar was operated immediately-adjacent to the BLWP.

6f) Temperature, Humidity and Winds (THAW) - DJH

This was a multi-instrument campaign, which was conducted between 23rd November and 4th December 2009. The main objective was to increase the understanding of clear-air radar returns - with the hope of eventually being able to retrieve profiles of temperature and humidity from the signal power. A secondary objective was to validate the performance of a Buck hygrometer, which was flown on the FAAM aircraft. The aircraft made overflights of the MST radar site on the afternoon of 30th November, when the tropopause was particularly low. This provided the aircraft with a rare opportunity to encounter lower-stratospheric air, for which the contributions of humidity to refractive index can be ignored. Radiosondes were launched every 2 hours from the radar site. Although it had been a cloudy day, the skies cleared just as the aircraft arrived overhead. This allowed the Raman lidar to be operated from 17:00 UT through till 06:00 UT the following morning. HAC had previously calibrated the lidar as part of her PhD work. The calibration was fine-tuned by comparing radiosonde measurements with lidar data

averaged over one hour to either side of the radiosonde launch time. The correlations between humidity were very good (lidar data were ignored for the overlap altitude region 0 - 2 km).

7. Any Other Business

The Met Office will be conducting an intensive FUND observation period during the last 2 weeks of July 2010.

No provisional date was set for the next meeting, which is likely to be held during the latter part of January 2011.